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inclusion of analytical accounts, provides the opportunity to determine the final financial results of the specific activity of the educational institution by calculating the income and expenses received from the higher education institutions according to the activities.

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THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF ESTABLISHING NEW TECHNOLOGIES ON PERSONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract:

Objective. It consists in the development of scientific and practical recommendations and proposals for improving team management processes in the service sector.

Methods. This article uses the methods of scientific observation, abstract-logical thinking, conversation, statistical, economic, financial, and expert assessment. The reliability of the information base used in this article is explained by the fact that they are obtained from official sources, and the reliability of the developed proposals and recommendations is explained by the level of compliance with the priority directions and programs of the development of our republic. Relevant conclusions in the field have been adopted into practice by official organizations.

Results. The scientific significance of the research results is explained by the fact that the theoretical-methodological and methodological apparatus for the further development of the improvement of team management processes in industry, service and other fields has been formed from the developed scientific-practical proposals. The conclusions and theoretical knowledge obtained on the improvement of team management processes in the service sector can be used as a scientific resource in the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other enterprises in the service sector.

Conclusions. Team management in the service sector reaches a high level of improvement of skills, and as a result of active activities and special training, its increase occurs. The worker is interested

in imparting his knowledge to the youth. This period is characterized by self-sacrifice from the creative side, in which it is possible to rise to new levels of service.

Keywords: Human resources, management, personnel, innovation, employees, skills, economic sectors.

Introduction. In the leading sectors of the economy of the countries of the world, in particular, in industry, great attention is paid to the issues of following modern management principles in the processes related to team management. As a result, effective organization of the management structure of the team in the economic sectors of most countries of the world remains one of the most important tasks today. Scientific research including introducing modern corporate management methods in the management of companies, establishing effective forms of corporate relations in them, developing innovative models of team management, formation of management relations as a system covering social and spiritual aspects, mental abilities and values of a person, directions for motivating team work in the enterprise and strengthening

management principles aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the use of an effective method of managing the enterprise team remains the main current issues in the world.

In modern literature, especially in the management of teams in enterprises, the attitude to the object of research is expressed in different ways. Perhaps this is suitable for the modern age. In our opinion, the principles and methods used can be effective only with a clear idea of the object of the management process. For example, nowadays in literature and practice, "Human resources", "Labor resources", "Personnel", "Employees", "Team representatives", "Experts" and other phrases are widely used. In order to clarify, we expressed our opinion graphically. (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. Management of Human factor and labor team

As can be seen from the figure, management objects are divided into four groups, and the main, comprehensive group is human resources management. This object is mainly a macroeconomic indicator and plays an important role in solving problems between the world and

countries (growth of human resources, population composition, their social protection, development, etc). Human resources include all human resources in the world and countries, and it has its own management tasks. Labor resources are mainly limited to the circle of people who

have the ability to work. Of course, this indicator may have different limits in many countries. For example, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the population with labor resources from the age of 18 to the retirement age (men up to 60 years, women up to 54 years) is considered to be able to work.

Methods. Scientific research, abstract-logical thinking, interview, statistical, economic, economic, expert methods are used to check the scientific and practical importance of research. The reliability of the information base produced in this article is that they are taken from official sources, and the reliability of the proposals and recommendations is the development of the priority directions and programs of our republic. Sohaqaoid is accepted into the official practice of the relevant approved.

Employees are those who are actually working, or in other words, the part of the labor resources recorded in the organizational list of organizations. When we say "organization", we mean enterprises operating from private entrepreneurship to large state enterprises.

Taking into account the national characteristics, the scientific-theoretical and methodological foundations of team management processes in Uzbekistan's economic sectors, in particular, in the field of direct service, were developed by B.Khodiev, S.Gulomov, N.Yuldoshev, A.Bekmuradov, M.Ikramov, SH. It is widely covered in the works of Zaynutdinov, M.Mahkamova, R.Nurimbetov, SH.Mirsaidova, Y.Goldman.

Directly in our republic, there are still no well-founded and clearly developed methods for evaluating personnel management processes in the industry, service sector, there is a need to research the structure and socio-economic essence of personnel management processes in the service sector, to develop methods of team management processes in industry

enterprises. Methods of evaluation and management of innovative potential of enterprises are insufficiently researched as an independent research object.

In this article, as theoretical and methodological bases, relevant laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the field, decrees, decisions and works of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers, fundamental works related to the further increase of the innovative potential in the industry and service sector in our country, innovative works of national and foreign scientists of industrial enterprises the works written on the improvement of management methods and assessment of potential served.

Results and Discussion.

Employees include all labor resources in the organization according to the traditional distribution, including personnel and others. The labor team is a group of working people of the organization and is divided into specific groups (managers, workers, service providers, students, etc). Personnel is an employee with a certain specialty, potential and ability. In our opinion, every employee cannot be called a Staff, because it is related to the way of working, knowledge, and intelligence. Personnel management (human resource management) is a set of activities for selection, training, organizing the activities of the organization's employees, wages and other social and spiritual activities. The master Amir Temur wrote in his books that "I have seen in my experience that one person who is business-minded, has courage and enthusiasm, is determined, entrepreneurial and alert, is better than thousands of inactive and indifferent people, because one experienced person gives work to a thousand people."¹ Selection of employees and their rational management is one of the most responsible tasks in the activity of any organization. Several issues related to the

¹ Amir Temur. «Institutes of Temur», p..25 .

theory of personnel management (principles of work, inclination to it, new methods of management, identification of the need for personnel, their selection, recruitment, work with them, training, business career and training of reserve personnel, conflicts and their management) were considered in our previous book. In this book, we decided to consider other issues related to the theory of personnel management. McKay, the author of the recruitment method, noted, "I have never seen a person with a bad reference letter."

Such papers will remain as papers. Every leader must be a psychologist. When hiring in Japan, first of all, a person's knowledge is considered. The information presented in the personal statement is thoroughly studied. Good work experience and special expertise are required to work as a senior manager in American and European countries. Enterprises and organizations have different approaches to managing their employees. Table 1. compares some indicators of the Japanese and American approaches in this direction.

Table 1.

American and Japanese approach to managing employees of enterprises and organizations

№	Criteria for working in the organization	Japanese approach	American approach
1	The basis of organization	Matching	Efficiency
2	Attitude to work	The main thing is to fulfill the obligation	The main thing is to fulfill the obligation
3	Rivalry	Not in practice	Strong
4	Guarantee for the employee	High (lifetime hire)	Low
5	Decision making	Bottom up	Top down
6	Delegation of authority	Kam holatda	Keng tarqalgan
7	Dealing with subordinates	Family	Official
8	Recruitment method	After graduation	By work qualities
9	Paying for labor	Based on work experience	By work results

Recruiting good employees for any organization is a complex and multi-step process. It includes scientifically based principles and methods of operation. Below we consider the main issues of personnel management services that deal with this problem. This involves several steps:

1. Personnel planning. It consists in determining the demand for human resources, considering the future development of the organization. Of course, when creating such a strategic plan, it is necessary to take into account the changes that will happen with the employees who are currently working. These changes may include::

- promotion of employees;

- leave for work; to be sent to other enterprises for study and business trip;
- retirement and other factors. In other words, it will be necessary to draw up a strategic plan of personnel management. In addition to the above factors, it is necessary to take into account the use of internal resources and the traditions of the organization.

2. Dispatch of team members. Searching for and attracting potential employees from among specialists, creating a personnel reserve is a permanent main task. For this purpose, it is advisable to use various information systems and communication tools widely. This is a large and complex service that

requires constant attention and deep knowledge.

3. Selection of employees for the team. Evaluating candidates for vacancies taking into account specialization, business and human characteristics is a very complicated issue. It works well to involve supervisors in the evaluation of such candidates, especially supervisors in the area where the recruitment is intended. Selection and confirmation of the reserve personnel created by the team management colleagues gives a good result.

4. Determination of monthly salary and benefits. It is fair to set wages and benefits based on the performance and contribution of each employee. It is desirable to develop and use an objective and flexible system.

5. Skill building. It includes the fact that the hired employees are engaged in the effective operation of the organization, diligently fulfill the tasks that the employee must perform, and others. The further improvement of the psychological environment in the team, the creation of comfortable conditions in the workplace and production environment are of great importance for the formation of skills in employees.

6. Team training. Training of qualified specialists, development of new programs, as well as their effective use, periodic retraining of employees in order to increase and develop professional knowledge in the team is considered necessary. This process involves several issues:

- a) studying new proposed manufacturing processes;
- b) learning foreign languages;

First direction:

a) social protection of the team employee (constant health care, ensuring timely rest, improvement of living conditions and organization of reasonable nutrition);

v) having advanced production experiences in our republic and abroad;

g) internship in advanced enterprises of the republic and abroad;

d) providing and getting acquainted with new literature on the specialty.

7. Management of the employee's professional growth. It is necessary to create such conditions that each employee can satisfy his interests and requirements while bringing great benefits to the organization he works for.

8. Personnel certification. To develop a method of objective assessment of the work results of each specialist in quantitative and qualitative indicators, to determine the level of his specialization. It is necessary to involve the leading employees of the duty service and departments in this work, and to familiarize the employee with the attestation documents and results in a timely manner.

9. Placement of employees. Based on the results of the attestation, solving the issue of redeployment of employees according to the staff list (upgrading the position ladder, leaving in place, downgrading, transferring from one workplace to another workplace and dismissal).

10. Training of management personnel. Improving the leadership skills and level of senior staff includes the problems of program development, experience of working with employees and their concentration, as well as creating a pool of personnel among young employees.

Issues in the team's personnel management service include organizing work with employees in two directions. These directions include as follows:

b) advanced team employee reward programs (awards, labels, referrals, titles, orders, etc.);

v) development of instructions and suggestions to the manager on improving working conditions, ensuring the creation of

a creative psychological environment in the team.

Second direction — law and disciplinary direction - covers a wide range of issues of interaction between the team and management (labor relations, disputes, conflicts, instructions for managers and employees, bilateral contracts, applications of various contents, etc.)

Being a team leader is very difficult. Therefore, their thoughts, outlook, spirituality, character, and mentality are also different. Of course, the leader will have to keep an eye on their various good and bad works, so that no work is left out of their sight. If a leader is only busy with management and his personality, and is indifferent to monitoring the people under his command, then this leader should be abandoned. Not being aware of the behavior of the members of their institution leads to the division of the team into several parties. Such a leader will harm both the state and the community.

Conclusions. Team management in the service sector reaches a high level of improvement of skills, and as a result of active activities and special training, its increase occurs. The worker is interested in imparting his knowledge to the youth. This period is characterized by self-sacrifice from the creative side, in which it is possible to rise to new levels of service.

- A person achieves his independence and the highest peak of self-expression. Respect for oneself, respect for others who have achieved their position through honest work, respect for oneself and others will increase. Although most of the employee's requirements have been met by this time, he is interested in the level of wages, and interest in income from other sources increases.

- The final stage lasts from 60 to 65 years. The employee begins to prepare for retirement. During this period, finding a

reliable successor and training the candidate for the vacating position will increase. Although this period is characterized by a career crisis (the employee begins to feel discomfort from a mental and physical point of view, getting less satisfaction from work). Self-expression and respect for self and others are elevated to a higher level. The employee is interested in maintaining the level of salary while trying to increase income from other sources, which will provide a good supplement to the pension income as salary replacement funds before retirement.

- At the next benefit stage, the job level (type of activity) in this enterprise is completed. There are opportunities for self-expression in other types of activities, which were realized only as a hobby of interest without being realized while working at the enterprise (painting, gardening, working in public enterprises, animal husbandry, etc.).

- Respect for oneself and respect for retired people increases. However, financial ethics and health dictates the need for income from other sources and ongoing health care.

- Career management requires a full understanding of what happens in people and a study of the various career stages. Special research is conducted for these purposes, and includes enterprises interested in effective career management.

- Some of the research results are formalized in a special form called careerogram, and clearly represent the manager's path through the career ladder.

- Every person plans his future based on his requirements and taking into account the socio-economic conditions that have arisen. It is no surprise that he wants to have clear information about his future career growth and development opportunities in this company, as well as what he will do to achieve this.

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SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF UZBEK NATIONAL ART OF EMBROIDERY

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Abstract : The article describes the modern development directions of embroidery based on the study of the unique features of the Uzbek national embroidery art. The directions of modern development of embroidery have been determined based on research with students studying design.

Key words: Embroidery, pattern, tools, floral decorations, needle, needle, national values, practical art.

Introduction. Embroidery - needle on | decorative art or craft. The art of fabric or other materials yarn through is a | embroidery has developed over the

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